

USE OF BIO-DESIGN IN APARTMENT INTERIOR DESIGN

In the interior design of an apartment, customers, turning to designers, often want to get psychological comfort from the space in which they will live. The use of biodesign in his work helps the designer to achieve the customer's wishes and create a comfortable space. Biodesign refers to the practice of using principles found in nature to create more sustainable and environmentally friendly design solutions.

Overall, biodesign can bring numerous benefits to the interior design process, from improving air quality and well-being to sustainability and aesthetic appeal. By using natural elements in design, designers can create a more harmonious and healthy environment for residents.

The work shows the use of biodesign in the interior design of the apartment. When working with customers, almost everyone wants to incorporate natural elements into the future environment to create a harmonious atmosphere. Flowers, plants, or bionic forms that imitate the environment are used in almost every apartment, at the request of the customer. And all this is usually done in some unique style, be it some kind of designer pot, or just an adaptation of vegetation to the interior or landscape (for example, ivy on the wall, or a lawn on the terrace of an apartment).

An example of visualization of an apartment project using biodesign in which people will live in the future is given. Visualization is performed using the software product 3ds Max (3D Studio MAX) is a three-dimensional graphic editor, a full-featured professional application, a system for creating and editing objects and creating visualizations, developed by Autodesk. Contains state-of-the-art tools for architects, designers, artists and multimedia professionals.

Figure 1 shows a part of the current interior design of the "Terrace with Lawn" apartment.

Rice. 1 Interior project of the "Terrace with lawn" apartment

The proposed interior design of the apartment is not an economical option. Used principles found in nature to create a more sustainable and environmentally friendly design solution with more care in use. But all these questions are covered by the feeling of a person who goes out to this terrace in the evening, and can walk barefoot on the green grass, sit on the couch and relax surrounded by the "green" natural background without leaving his apartment.